

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>TOSHE - Test Of Systems for Harsh Environment</i>
Project TA identifier <i>Example: TA1-11 (1st TA call, experiment 11)</i>	TA1-13
General application	<i>Space, high-reliability applications, memory characterization, microprocessor characterization</i>
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Luigi DILILLO, CNRS-LIRMM</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>29/11/2021 to 02/12/2021</i>
Facility	<i>PSI (Proton Irradiation Facility - PIF), Switzerland</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>15 hours</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The WP06/JRA2 main objective and contribution is to develop methodologies to enhance observability of complex systems, remote testing, research of environmental conditions to achieve best experimental success, data collection, and processing. In this context, the submitters performed tests in several complex systems at two different levels: complex devices and Systems-on-a-Chip (SoCs).

In this first Transnational Access, counting with the collaboration of several teams and institutions, the submitters carried out experiments in the Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI) facilities. These experiments focused on high-energy protons and were segmented into three main branches targeting different aspects of system-level testing:

- University of Montpellier (UM) - LIRMM, focusing on the characterization and testability of memories;
- Carlos III University of Madrid (UC3M), targeting application benchmarks such as Dual Core Macrosynchronized Lockstep with rollback and Reduced Precision Redundancy FFT, evaluation of Soft Error Mitigation (SEM) IP Core;
- and German Aerospace Center (DLR), characterization of caches influence on SoC running an Linux operating system.

It is important to note that the original submission request prospected 44 hours of beam time for the execution of several experiments. Since the granted time was shorter (15 hours), some experiments addressed in the proposal were reduced in scope to accommodate that difference. The granted beam time was equally divided among the submitters.

Experiment test report

This report provides a summary of each experiment and presents some preliminary results. The topics are segmented concerning each experiment leading institution. Also, general information about the test facility is provided.

Test Facility

The experiments were performed in the Proton Irradiation Facility (PIF), part of Switzerland's Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI). The facility was constructed to test spacecraft components, and it can generate proton energies relevant to harsh space environments. During the test campaign, the instruments were configured to generate protons with energies up to 230 MeV, targeting different fluxes. In order to reach lower energies, metal plates were placed in the beam path to reduce the energy of the protons. The beam homogeneity was checked for each energy setting, and the reported proton fluence variation on the DUTs is estimated to be less than 10%. The experiments were performed at room temperature.

University of Montpellier (UM) - LIRMM

The LIRMM group performed two concurrent experiments: evaluation of a self-refresh DRAM (PSRAM – Pseudo-Static Random-Access Memories) memory and a comparative study of SDRAM memories. The first experiment evaluates a device that recently reached the market using a setup based on the Zynq-7000 SoC from Xilinx. It targets the characterization under static and dynamic test modes. The second experiment is a comparative study of different generations of memory devices for assessing the fault mechanisms under radiation and understanding the impact of geometry, used materials, and manufacturing nodes across these generations. In this case, the DUTs are three SDRAMs by ISSI, candidates to be used in ESA space missions, placed in a compact board design.

Self-Refresh DRAM Experiment

This experiment extended the studies analyzing the effects under high-energy protons to compare the fault mechanisms with the results obtained for neutron particles. In order to achieve that, it is presented and discussed the event cross-sections for each fault type and energy. The DUT is a DRAM memory manufactured by Infineon Technologies, the S27KS0642GABHI020. The device is designed with a 38 nm high-speed CMOS technology with a maximum operation clock of 200 MHz. It is commercially known as HyperRAM™ and its interface as HyperBus™, due to a self-refresh mechanism that performs refresh operations to keep the content of the cell without the controller intervention.

A controller board based on the Zynq-7000 SoC from Xilinx was used to implement the HyperBus™ interface and enable the execution of test algorithms. A daughterboard was used to connect the DUT to the controller. The controller is composed of a configurable System-on-Chip (SoC) architecture, which provides: a Cortex™-A9 processor, used for tests execution; several peripherals for communication and development; and the SoC's programmable logic, in which an IP (Intellectual Property) provided by Infineon manages the communication between the processor and the DUT. An external current monitor was utilized during the experiment to identify Single Event Latch-up (SEL) events. This experiment employed dynamic testing of the memory, in which write and read operations are executed under irradiation, generating radiation-induced upset events during active utilization of the DUT.

In order to analyze the error data, two approaches were used: logical bitmaps to provide an overview of the errors and their patterns, and cross-section plots for measuring the occurrence of the events. The found proton-induced events have the same classification as ones from previous works focusing on neutron effects: SBUs, stuck bits, and SEFIs (block errors). *Figure 1* presents the cross-sections for the different fault types with respect to each energy tested.

Figure 1 - Estimated SBUs, stuck bits, and block errors cross-section for each energy value. The error bars represent a 95% confidence interval with a 10% beam fluence uncertainty.

For SBUs and stuck bits, the number of events increased with the energy. For all energies, the cross-section for stuck bits is higher than the ones for SBUs. In dynamic mode, where the cells are constantly accessed with write and read operations, a similar behavior was found on the same memory under thermal and atmospheric-like neutron spectra. Besides the SBUs and stuck bits, block errors were observed at 230 MeV, but not for the lower energies. Since the number of block errors events at 230 MeV was very low (giving the high error bars), the probability of having the same type of events in the lower energies should not be discarded.

In this experiment, the effects of high-energy protons in a self-refresh DRAM were investigated and the main objectives were achieved. Future work intends to investigate the retention time of the tested samples to better understand the memory cells degradation and to obtain a better correlation with previous studies.

SDRAM Experiment

This study studied three generations of SDRAMs from one manufacturer, with different technology node sizes. The tested components were ISSI 512 Mb SDRAMs of three generations: IS42S86320B with node size 110 nm; the 72 nm IS42S86320D; and the 63 nm IS42S86320F. The components were mounted on dedicated test boards, each board housing three components: one sample of each node size. Apart from the DUTs, the test boards housed a system-on-chip FPGA from Microsemi, a SmartFusion2 M2S025, as the main controller unit. Static and dynamic test procedures were utilized during irradiation with a rotating schedule among the three samples on each test board. A dynamic test was running on one sample at all times, while the other two samples were performing static tests.

During proton irradiation, SBUs and stuck bits were observed. An example of how bits with errors as a function of proton fluence during tests with the dynamic mode is shown in *Figure 2*. This figure's increasing trend of errors is due to accumulating stuck bits in the memory over the test duration. Regions of fluence with protons of energies 230 MeV, 70 MeV, and 151 MeV are marked. Cross-sections separated in stuck bits and SBUs for the tested energies are presented in *Figure 3*. Model D and F have similar cross-sections, while model B has a higher error cross-section than the other models. The stuck bit cross-sections are higher than the SBU cross-sections for all memories, as is seen for DUT B1 in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2 - Example of the error trends found in one DUT during dynamic testing.

Figure 3 - Error cross-sections for SBUs (top) and stuck bits (bottom) for the different memory models.

Carlos III University of Madrid (UC3M)

The UC3M experiments focused on the evaluation of Single Event Effects (SEE) in SoCs (System-on-Chip) COTS (Commercial Off-The-Shelf) devices. To this purpose, the selected target board was a commercial Zybo board featuring a Xilinx Zynq 7000 SoC device, namely an XC7Z010-1CLG400C. This device includes a Processing System (PS) with a dual-core ARM Cortex A9 processor running at 600 MHz and an SRAM-based FPGA. The experiment's goal was to test benchmarks that were previously tested using other beams to compare results and evaluate the feasibility of the test setup under different conditions. Two benchmarks were tested:

- For the Programmable Logic, two implementations of a hardened-by-design FFT block were selected.
- For the Processing System, it was selected a dual-core Macrosynchronized Lockstep with rollback, with a lightweight OS (FreeRTOS) and without it (baremetal).

The SoC is the main element of the Zybo Development Board. The benchmarks run the experiments continuously and check the results against golden references. Upon error, the results are sent through a UART connection to an external host kept in the irradiation chamber, but distant from the target device, to ensure that it is not affected by the radiation. The host is a Raspberry Pi device that can be accessed remotely from outside the bunker using an Ethernet connection. The supervisor script run in the Raspberry Pi is in charge of receiving and storing the outputs of the benchmarks in the Zynq, as well as resetting and reprogramming the FPGA when an error is detected or the microprocessor stops responding. The resetting is performed by cutting off the power to the Zybo. The Raspberry Pi controls that action using a set of relays attached to some of its pins.

FPGA Benchmark

The main goal in this part of the experiment was to compare the performance of some hardening techniques that were already tested with lower energy protons. Due to some problems with the beam, this part of the campaign was shorter than expected, and only two designs were tested at PSI: the Scaled

RPR R2²SDF FFT and the TMR R2²SDF FFT architecture. For comparison, the results of the two different campaigns are presented, the one at PSI (230 MeV protons) and the one carried out previously at Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (CNA, Sevilla) (15 MeV protons). The beam parameters for these benchmarks were the energy of 230 MeV and flux of $1.4 \cdot 10^8$ p/cm²/s.

Table 1 presents the quantitative analysis of the faults found during the experiments. The first two columns of the table correspond to the scaled RPR benchmark, while the last two columns display the results of the TMR benchmark. In the rows of the table, two main metrics were collected: the error cross-section and the uncorrectable error cross-section. The error cross-section was defined as the number of faulty FFT calculations, this is, a fault in any of the triplicated FFTs, regardless of whether it reaches the voted output, divided by the fluence of the beam. The uncorrectable error cross-section is defined as the number of uncorrectable errors divided by the fluence of the beam.

	Scaled RPR R2 ² SDF FFT		TMR R2 ² SDF FFT	
	PSI	CNA	PSI	CNA
Radiation time (min)	36	30	14	30
Faulty frames	86	176	52	180
Cross-section (10^{-10} cm²)	2.84 (2.24, 3.44)	2.75 (2.3, 3.2)	4.42 (3.22, 5.62)	1.86 (1.6, 2.1)
Uncorrectable frames	5	7	3	4
Uncorrectable cross section (10^{-11} cm²)	1.65 (0.54, 3.86)	1.09 (0.44, 2.25)	2.55 (0.53, 7.46)	0.41 (0.11, 1.06)

Table 1 - Results from the irradiation experiments

According to this data, it is possible to establish that higher energies are responsible for higher cross-sections, both in total errors found and in uncorrectable errors. This difference is more notable in the TMR version of the circuit, although the test at PSI was shorter in duration, resulting in wider confidence intervals. This was the expected result since the DUTs are at different zones of the SEU cross-section vs. LET curve.

Dual Core Lock-Step in Processing System Benchmark

This part of the experiment aims to evaluate a fault tolerance technique developed by the UC3M research group: the Macro-synchronized Lockstep (MSLS). This technique has been previously evaluated with fault injection campaigns, as well as low-energy proton irradiation. The hardened system has self-recovery capabilities supported with a software-based macro synchronization approach. It uses spatial redundancy, so that application execution runs in parallel in several cores but without micro synchronization (i.e., it is not required that the cores execute the same instruction at the same time exactly). After the task or program is completed on all functional cores, the results must be checked to decide if errors have occurred.

The approach implements recovery processes (rollbacks). When errors are detected, the rollback process restores the microprocessor from a previous error-free state. In contrast to other approaches, this hardening approach permits consecutive rollbacks with adjustable depth. If a rollback process is not able to restore the system correctness, another rollback to the previous error-free state (consecutive rollback) will be tried. The hardened system can detect incorrect behaviors and eventually trigger a software reset if needed. Additionally, the proposed approach can restore the system from exceptions since the exception table was modified to handle all exceptions and recover the system from any possible event. A watchdog

timer was used to supervise the microprocessor execution. In the case of a hang, the watchdog restarts the system.

The proposed approach was evaluated in the irradiation campaign using protons with an energy of 230 MeV and a flux of $1.4 \cdot 10^8$ p/cm²/s for both baremetal and OS-based versions. The experimental results are shown in *Table 2*, which has the same three categories mentioned in the previous section: Errors, Detected errors, and Cross-section. Experimental irradiation results demonstrate again the high error coverage of the hardened system (up to 99.2%), in accordance with the results of the previous irradiation campaign.

	Category	Baremetal	OS
Errors	Undetected errors	3 (0.8%)	8 (2.3%)
	Detected errors	392 (99.2%)	341 (97.7%)
	Total errors	395 (100.0%)	349 (100.0%)
Detected errors	Corrected errors	215 (54.8%)	112 (32.8%)
	WDT	85 (21.7%)	139 (40.8%)
	SW Reset	92 (23.5%)	90 (26.4%)
Cross-section (cm²)	Total errors	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-09}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-09}$
	Undetected errors	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-11}$

Table 2 – PSI irradiation campaign results

Table 3 presents the rollback distribution for PSI experiments, which gives the same trends found in previous results with low-energy protons.

		Baremetal	OS
Successful rollbacks	1 rollback	206 (95.8%)	103 (92.0%)
	2 rollbacks	8 (3.7%)	9 (8.0%)
	3 rollbacks	1 (0.5%)	0

Table 3 – PSI rollback distribution

The experiments performed at PSI were successful, and the results agreed with previous experiments carried out at CNA with lower energy protons. They also showed a good agreement with fault injection campaigns. The irradiation test was also very useful to prove that the current setup can be used in another facility with different conditions and energies. So far, this setup has been used successfully under protons of very different energies (15 MeV and 230 MeV), using on-site and remote operation. In the future, it is planned to perform additional experiments in other facilities to compare the results and continue improving the system testing approach and setup.

German Aerospace Center (DLR)

The DLR experiment investigates and analyzes the behavior of central processing unit (CPU) caches under proton irradiation. The used DUT was the Zynq-7000 from Xilinx with its two ARM Cortex A9

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processing cores and two cache levels. This study created a customized embedded Linux operating system, which included a low-level debugger to store crash reports for later analysis. Additionally, a short instruction was written in software to generate a high cache utilization and observe single event upsets (SEU) in the stored data. The Zynq-7000 has two cache levels, L1 and L2. The first level, L1 is a cache for each individual CPU core and is split into data cache (L1d) and instruction cache (L1i). The second level, L2 is a shared cache between both CPUs. As the caches are made to be transparent for the user and the cache content itself cannot directly be accessed, an indirect measurement had to be made. Hence, three different cache configurations were operated to correlate the cause of occurring errors. The measurement used beam energy of 230 MeV and a maximum flux of 2×10^9 protons/cm²/second. The beam was focused only on the DUT to avoid irradiation of any other components on the board like the DDR3-SDRAM or NAND flash memory.

The test procedure is divided into three different configurations: (1) all caches enabled; (2) L1 instruction and L1 data cache enabled, L2 disabled; and (3) L1 and L2 caches disabled. Every configuration followed the same test sequence. At first, the test object needs to be completely booted and start the software execution before the beam can be enabled. As soon as the board or software crashes, the beam is immediately halted, and crash reports are generated. Once the board is power-cycled and brought back to a nominal state, the flow will restart, and the run can be continued.

The Zynq-7000 has two ARM cortex A9 CPUs with an individual 4-way associative L1 instruction and data cache, each containing 32 kilobytes. The shared L2 cache is 8-way associative and has a size of 512 kilobytes. Hence, the size of the data array to be held in the cache for the test was chosen to be a maximum of one quarter of the size of the caches to occupy only one section. Both caches also have a parity bit already built-in, providing a small countermeasure to SEUs. With this cache structure, the idea was to create a data array with a conservative size of 4 kilobytes. To keep the data array permanently in the cache, it was continuously summed up and compared. To avoid any unwanted optimizations from the compiler, the array was generated during runtime based on random numbers.

To analyze the system and get an error report after a crash, the Linux kernel GNU debugger (KGDB) was used. The KGDB allows the user to access parts of the system after a severe kernel panic. It is automatically started and entered after a crash. The access can be made either through a serial console or remotely via Ethernet. The serial access was chosen as this option was easier and more reliable. During the test, it was clearly observed that the time to crash did increase with more deactivated caches. Occasionally, the used kernel debugger couldn't be accessed after a crash or did not return any valuable information. But in 37 of the 50 crashes, a useful report was created. The types of crash and error state did differ between different cache configurations. For the cache content itself, which was tested with a checksum and sent via Ethernet, any evidence of SEUs was found. Only once a bit flip occurred in a single byte and was therefore not used for further evaluation or analysis.

L1 Enabled, L2 Enabled:

In the first run, all caches were enabled. With a total of 25 crashes, a useful error report could be produced for 18 of them. Looking at the process counter after a crash, it always pointed at a kernel memory address (ranged at 0xC0000000). This means that the crash appeared while a kernel function was accessed. This corresponds with the CPU mode, which was always in Supervisor Call (SVC). The kernel panic message after the crash came down to 16 cases of an unhandled prefetch abort, once an undefined string and once a data abort. The average time to crash was 19 seconds. The target fluence was selected to 1.3×10^9 protons/cm² and a corresponding SEFI cross-section of 1.92×10^{-8} cm²/device has been calculated.

L1 Enabled, L2 Disabled:

In this run, the individual CPU data and instruction caches L1 were disabled, while the shared L2 stayed enabled. In total, 20 crashes were documented, and 15 produced a usable report. The process counter pointed again most of the time at a kernel memory address, except for two occasions where it pointed to an unused address. For one of these occasions, the CPU mode also did reside in an Undefined mode. Otherwise, the CPU mode was again constantly in SVC. In contrast to the first run, the crashing kernel messages changed to unhandled paging request, null pointer dereference, page domain fault, alignment exception, and a bad mode. The bad mode message coincided with the CPU being stuck in an undefined mode, as mentioned before. The occurrence of these messages is depicted in *Figure 4* below.

Figure 4 - Linux kernel panic messages after crash

L1 Disabled, L2 Disabled:

In the third run, all caches were disabled. Due to time constraints, only 10 crashes were documented and only 4 of them produced a usable report. This time, the process counter did point only once into the kernel area, all other times, the address was outside any reasonable memory (e.g., 0xFFFF0000). The CPU mode also was just once in SVC and in all the other cases, either Undefined or Abort. The same holds true for the kernel panic message, which returned three times a bad mode (either data or prefetch abort) and once unable to handle paging requests (in SVC mode). In this configuration, a SEFI cross-section of 1.52×10^{-10} cm²/device has been determined and the average time to crash was 71 seconds.

Looking at the results with a general view, the different cache configurations lead to quite different crash cases. Not just in the time to crash or SEFI cross-section, which differed significantly (up to 80x), but also in the resulting kernel and debug information. It is clear that with a running operating system underneath to ensure that everything is running stable independent from the user program, the crash basically never comes from the executed user program, but from the kernel itself. The reason can be wrong addresses or wrong register values during execution. Most crashes do not occur due to false cache data, but in large processing pipelines.

It was seen that with fewer cache levels activated, the time to crash was increased and the SEFI cross-sections were lower. The crash reports by the KGDB delivered useful information by being consistent with the type of crash in each configuration. The crash reports did match the expectation of the respective configuration. This can give basic approaches for future mitigation techniques, for example by handling wrong addresses differently or by disabling critical features without much performance loss.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

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